

DELAYS IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS: CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract

Construction projects are becoming increasingly complex due to frequent cost overruns, which often lead to delays, incomplete works, or other operational challenges. In the Nepali construction industry, traditional management approaches are still widely practiced across most projects. Identifying critical success factors is therefore essential to develop effective strategies for minimizing costs and improving project performance. The main objective of this research is to explore the key factors contributing to cost overruns and to identify the critical causes and effects of delays in construction projects. To achieve this, consultants and contractors were interviewed using structured questionnaires to capture practical insights, and the collected responses were analyzed to propose suitable methodologies for the Nepali context. The findings suggest that modifications in project management practices are vital for ensuring timely completion. High managerial performance, standard management procedures, adoption of modern tools, effective time and quality management, and active team involvement were identified as significant contributors to project success. Moreover, six major factors affecting delays were recognized; time overruns, cost overruns, disputes, arbitration, total project abandonment, and litigation with time and cost overruns being the most frequent and critical outcomes of such delays.

Keywords: Cause; consultant; delay; effect; project

I. Background

The construction industry has great impact on economy of all countries (Assaf, Al-Khalil, & Al-Hazmi, 1995). It is one of the sectors that provides crucial ingredient for the development of nations' economy (Alnuaimi & Mohsin, 2013). During execution of construction projects, the works proceed at a slower pace than planned, and delays frequently appear. Their appearance leads to additional cost generation, conflicts among project participants (Raahed, Haq, & Aslam, 2013). The construction industry in many countries accounts for 6-9 percent of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Challal & Tkouat, 2012); and according to Bhimaraya, (2001), it reaches up to 10 percent of the GDP of most countries. The construction industry plays vital role in the economy growth and has a significant effect on the efficiency and productivity of other industry sectors. One cannot think of widespread investment in manufacturing, agriculture, or service sectors unless the construction results of infrastructure facilities are in place. In some of the developing countries, the growth rate of construction activity outstrips that of population and of GDP (Maurice Paul Okeyo, Charles Mallans Rambo, & Paul Amollo Odundo, 2015).

Construction projects give rise to dissatisfaction to all the parties involved in the construction and the main role of the project manager is to make sure that the projects are completed within the allocated budget, time and cost achieving its quality specifications. Project implementation in Nepal has remained ineffective. Most development projects have failed to achieve the desired objectives. Time and cost overruns are common. The average delay in implementation of projects is about three years. It is eight years for energy projects, seven years for irrigation and transport projects (Agrawal, Subramanian, & Kapoor, 2010). One of the most important projects in Nepalese's scenario is the 'Melamchi Water supply project'. The project was started in 2001 A.D. with intended completion in 2006 A.D. Because of slow progress, the due date was extended to 2007 and recently, the project has set a new target at 2013 A.D and now the completion is again postponed to September 2016. And nobody knows how much will be added to the original cost as a result of the extensions. The World Bank (WB) withdrew its investment from the project in 2005 A.D because of the delays. This project is not still completed. Due to alleged mismanagement and incompetence of those in charge of implementing the project, the deadline for its completion has already been extended twice (Melamchi, 2012). However, the delays in the project continue to occur. The main purpose of this study is to identify the delay factors and their impact (effect) on project completion. Earlier studies either considered the causes or the effects of project delays, separately. This study takes an integral approach and attempts to analyze the impact of causes on effects. Some causes and effects of delays in construction projects can be country-specific (Alaryan, Elshahat, & Dawood, 2014).

This research has identified major causes of delay and categorized them as client-related, contractor- related, consultant-related, material-related, labor related, contract-related, contract relationship-related, and external factors. The study has also identified major effects of delay as: time overrun, cost overrun, dispute, arbitration, litigation, and total abandonment. Identification of causes and effects alone does not help the project managers to take appropriate remedial or preventive steps. The project managers need to understand, for example, what causes or factors result in time overrun or cost overrun. Therefore, the link between causes and effects of delays need to be established. Time overruns on infrastructure development projects during implementation continue to pose great challenges to developing countries (Divya.R & S.Ramya, 2015; Haseeb, Xinhai-Lu, Bibi, Maloof-ud-Dyian, & Rabbani, 2011; Honrao & Desai, 2015). Research has found that, there are many factors that impede on successful completion of projects

on time, budget, and quality (Pandey et al., 2015). This study sought to investigate on the factors that significantly contributed to time and cost overruns on construction projects. This evaluates relative ranking; and to quantify their impacts (Pourrostam, 2010). The study was based on a questionnaire survey among persons drawn from contractors, consultants and client, involved in the implementation of the projects in the study.

Research Objectives

- To determine the primary factors contributing to delays in construction projects.
- To examine the underlying sources of construction delays in projects within Nepal.
- To assess the impacts of delays on construction project outcomes.

II. Aspects on Mix Design

The research has been structured as the case study of construction projects during implementation phase aspects of Kathmandu valley. The entire process revolves around the secondary data sources collected from the organization's periodic publications, yearly reviews, customer feedback charts and market analysis of the company in competition to the others with same business process design. The study is based on descriptive research design followed by analytical approach to achieve the objective of the study. In the study, the universe of the data (the population) was the pool of information collected through the available project document sources and was kept under rigorous methods under study. The data was clustered and extracted for reference rather than random selection of data without clustering. Certain web based information and old data sources for reference were purely taken on judgment with assumption of higher inclination with the study, but maintained to be for purely referential purposes to avoid deviation of the mean (in theoretical terms).

The collection of data for the proposed study was collected from various sources in tabulated and non-tabulated (discretionary) forms. The sources of data gathered for the study were diverse and hence the study was based on the amount of information collected and tabulated from data sources as the organizational periodic publications, existing system design documents, market evaluation of the organization's products, customer feedback charts, progress charts, GANTT charts of the ongoing projects, PERT module depictions. The first beings were interviews with the representatives of the Construction Company and professionals working in the construction industry to collect the information. A questionnaire survey was conducted to obtain feedback from the construction industry. The collected data can be classified, depending on the sources and the accessibility as well as reliability of the sources, into two basic classifications: primary and secondary. The entire information gather are categorized as primary information. Next were the literature review to gather information about research topic and challenges faced by construction industry. It is obtained from the internet, articles in journals and papers and also some other published research book. From literature review, a clear framework of this research was established research work.

The data collection techniques followed during the process was best suitable with the circumstances prevalent and subjected to the restrictions of the regulations. They were: Personal interview of individuals of the organization under study, discussion with concerned authorities, onsite observations (non-participant), telephonic conversations, review of literatures (term-end analysis reports, long-term plan statements), Appraisals (success reviews, customer appraisals and feedbacks, project reviews) and assisting references (web-based information).

III. Materials Used

The developed survey questionnaire was distributed a fifty sets to the targeted respondent. About twenty tow sets were distributed to the contractors selected randomly from the list of “FCAN”, Federation of Contractors’ Association of Nepal and twenty eight sets were distributed to the consultants selected randomly from the list of “SCAEF”, the Society of Consulting Architect and Engineer Federation, Nepal. The procedure used in analyzing of data was aimed at establishing the relative importance of the various factors that contribute to causes of delays, effects of delays, and methods of minimizing construction delays. There are three steps used in analyzing the data: calculating the relative importance index; ranking of factors in each category based on relative importance index, and to determine degree of correlation on ranking the factors among the two groups. The objective of conducting the analysis for this section is to establish the factors under the groups of causes identified from the literature review and the ranking according to their significant influence towards construction project delays. A ranking method was used to achieve this objective and the significant of using these methods is it can reveal the most influential factors within each category of causes.

IV. Results and Discussion

A ranking method was employed to achieve this objective, with its main advantage being the ability to identify the most influential factors within each category of causes. A total of fifty-seven key factors contributing to construction delays were identified and categorized into eight major groups: material-related, labor-related, equipment-related, finance-related, contractor-related, client-related, consultant-related, and external factors. Within each group, these factors were ranked using the Relative Importance Index (RII) based on the perspectives of contractors and consultants.

Factors of Material Related Delays

There are seven factors that contributed to the causes of delays related to material delays were identified and ranked from the viewpoint of contractors and consultants. The Spearman’s Rank correlation coefficient, rho (rs) is 0.679 and has a significant value (Z) of 0.094.

Table 1: The result of factors of material delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Shortage of construction materials	4.2	1	4.24	1	rs = 0.679 Z =0.094 Thus H0 is accepted
Late delivery of materials	4.09	2	3.96	2	
Imported of construction materials	3.89	3	3.82	3	
Poor procurement of construction materials	3.85	4	3.6	4	
Poor quality of construction materials	3.7	5	3.73	5	
Escalation of material prices	3.57	6	3.71	6	
Unreliable	3.07	7	3.76	7	

Factors of Labor Related Delays

There are seven factors of labor related delays were ranked based on relative importance index from the perspective of contractor and consultants. The results of analysis show that factor of labor productivity is the top most significant factor that contributed to causes of delays among seven factors of labor related delay. The ranking between two groups of respondent of this category has the Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient; rho (rs) is 0.893 and a significant value (Z) of 0.007. Thus the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected and alternative hypothesis, H1 is accepted.

Table 2: The result of factors of labor related delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Slow mobilization of labor	3.86	4	3.76	5	rs = 0.893 Z =0.007 Thus rejected H0
Shortage of skill labor	4.09	2	3.98	2	
Labor productivity	4.11	1	4.00	1	
Labor supply	4.00	3	3.89	3	
Absenteeism	3.09	7	3.71	6	
Strike	3.30	6	3.31	7	
Low motivation/Morale	3.35	5	3.76	4	

Factors of Equipment Related Delays

Factors of causes of delays were ranked based on relative importance index from the viewpoint of contractor and consultant. Referring to this category has the Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient, rho (rs) is 0.764 and a significant value (Z) is 0.046. The null hypothesis, Ho is rejected and alternative hypothesis H1 is accepted. This shows that there is a significant degree of agreement between the ranking of the viewpoint of contractor and consultant.

Table 3: The result of factors of equipment related delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Insufficient number of equipments	4.46	1	4.4	1	rs = 0.764 Z =0.046 Thus H0 is accepted
Frequent equipment breakdown	4.33	2	4.18	2	
Shortage of equipment part	4.13	3	3.93	3	
Improper equipment	3.87	4	3.73	4	
Slow mobilization of equipment	3.85	5	3.76	5	
Equipment allocation problem	3.59	6	3.73	6	
Inadequate modern Equipment	3.3	7	3.76	7	

Factors of Finance Related Delays

There are seven factors that contributed to the causes of delays related to finance were ranked based on relative importance index. The results of relative importance index and the ranking of factors of finance related delays between respondent of contractor and consultant. In this category,

the null hypothesis, H₀ is rejected and alternative hypothesis, H₁ is accepted. The Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient, rho (rs) is 0.901 and has a significant value (Z) of 0.006. This value is much higher than 0.05 (5%) which rejected the alternative hypothesis, H₁ at a confidence level of 95%. Therefore, concluded that there is significant degree of agreement in the ranking among the groups of respondents.

Table 4: The result of factors of finance related delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Inadequate fund allocation	4.53	1	3.71	1	rs = 0.901 Z =0.006 Thus rejected H ₀
High interest rate	4.27	2	4.04	2	
Contractor's financial difficulties	3.95	3	3.87	3	
Unreasonable constraints to clients	3.8	4	3.79	4	
Delay payment to suppliers/subcontractors	3.67	5	3.76	5	
Monthly payment difficulties	3.09	6	3.71	6	
Client's financial difficulties	3.02	7	4.29	7	

Factors of Contractor Related Delays

The factors to causes of delays were ranked based on relative importance index between group of respondent of contractor and consultant. This category has the spearman's rank correlation coefficient, rho (rs) is 0.983 and a significant value (Z) is 0.001. The null hypothesis, H₀ is rejected and alternative hypothesis H₁ is accepted. This shows that there is a significant degree of agreement between the ranking of contractor and consultant.

Table 5: The result of factors of contractor related delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Inadequate contractor experience	4.54	1	4.36	1	rs = 0.983 Z =0.001 Thus H ₀ is rejected
Inappropriate construction methods	4.39	2	4.22	2	
Inaccurate time estimating	4.35	3	4.27	3	
Inaccurate cost estimating	4.29	4	4.23	4	
Poor site management and supervision	4.26	5	4.23	5	
Improper project planning and scheduling	4.23	6	4.16	6	
Incompetent project team	4.22	7	4.07	7	
Unreliable subcontractor	4.17	8	4.11	8	
Obsolete technology	3.83	9	3.79	9	

Factors of Client Related Delays

Both group of respondent agreed on the ranking of the factors based on relative importance index. The Spearman's Rank correlation, rho (rs) is 0.929, and significant value (Z) is 0.003, which indicates a significant agreement in the ranking hence the null hypothesis, Ho is rejected and alternative hypothesis, H1 is accepted.

Table 6: The result of factors of client related delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Slow decision making by client	4.39	1	4.32	1	rs = 0.929 Z =0.003 Thus H0 is rejected
Lack of experience	4.02	2	3.8	2	
Change orders	3.96	3	3.87	3	
Client interference	3.92	4	3.78	4	
Lack of capable representative	3.85	5	3.76	5	
Lack of communication and coordination	3.48	6	3.73	6	
Improper project feasibility study	3.08	7	3.76	7	

Factors of Consultant Related Delays

The results of survey analysis of factors of consultant related delays. Factors of causes of delays were ranked based on relative importance index between respondents of contractor and consultant. This category has the Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient, rho (rs) is 0.928 and a significant value (Z) is 0.008. The null hypothesis, Ho is rejected and alternative hypothesis H1 is accepted. This shows that there is a significant degree of agreement between the ranking of contractor and consultant.

Table 7: The result of factors of consultant related delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Inadequate consultant experience	3.98	1	4.02	1	rs = 0.928 Z =0.008 Thus rejected H0
Poor design and delay in design	3.93	2	3.84	2	
Inadequate project management assistance	3.76	3	3.76	3	
Slow response and poor inspection	3.52	4	3.76	4	
Incomplete drawing/detail design	3.46	5	3.71	5	
Inaccurate site investigation	3.43	6	3.73	6	

Factors of External Related Delays

There are seven factors of external related delays that contributed to the causes of delays were ranked based on relative importance index between contractor and consultant. The Spearman's Rank correlation coefficient, rho (rs) is 0.070 and significant value (Z) is 0.882 which much greater than 0.005. The null hypothesis, Ho is accepted and alternative hypothesis, H1 is rejected. This

shows that there is no significant degree of agreement in the ranking between both contractor and consultant perspective.

Table 8: The result of factors of external related delays

Factors	Consultant		Contractor		Spearman's Rank coeff. Rho (rs)
	Index	Rank	Index	Rank	
Unforeseen ground condition	4.07	1	3.91	1	rs = 0.070 Z = -0.882 Thus H ₀ is accepted
Unexpected geological condition	3.83	2	3.73	2	
Inflation/prices fluctuation	3.83	3	3.71	3	
Sloe site clearance	3.8	4	3.73	4	
Problem with neighbors	3.76	5	3.73	5	
Weather condition	3.57	6	3.76	6	
Conflict, War and public enemy	3.17	7	3.73	7	

Identification of the Major Causes of Delays

During a construction project, delays may result from many circumstances. In this research, based on data analyzed earlier, a total of fifty seven factors to causes of delays were grouped into eight groups of causes of delays in construction project. In order to identify the major delays groups or the major causes of delays, the group that causes delays was ranked based on mean value (the average indexes) between two group of respondent contractors and consultants. The following is a brief discussion of the groups to causes of delays according to the ranking of major delays groups.

Table 9: Ranking of major delays groups

No.	Groups	Consultant		Contractor		Overall	
		Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
1	Contractor	4.12	1	4.05	1	4.09	1
2	Equipment	3.93	2	3.92	2	3.93	2
3	Client	3.92	3	3.85	3	3.89	3
7	External	3.72	5	3.84	4	3.80	4
4	Material	3.76	4	3.83	5	3.77	5
5	Finance	3.7	6	3.8	6	3.74	6
6	Consultant	3.68	7	3.76	7	3.74	7
8	Labor	3.68	8	3.76	8	3.71	8

The Common Effects of Delays

In order to identify the effect of delays in construction project, there are six factors that effects delays were identified and ranked based on the mean value. Results shows that time overruns and cost overrun were the two most common effects of delays in construction project from the view of point of contractor and consultant.

Table 10: Ranking the common effects of delays

No.	Effects of Delay	Consultant	Contractor	Mean	Rank
		Index	Index		
1	Time Overrun	3.67	3.51	3.59	1
2	Cost overrun	2.54	2.76	2.65	2
3	Dispute	2.08	1.19	1.64	3
4	Total abandonment	1.98	1.2	1.59	4
5	Arbitration	1.04	1.02	1.04	5
6	Litigation	1.02	1.01	1.02	6

The major delays groups were identified and ranked, which group of contractor related delays is the top main groups that contribute to the causes of delays. From a total of fifty seven factors to causes of delays, twenty top most important factors have been identified. The top five most important factors that contributed to the causes of delays are factors of insufficient numbers of equipment, inaccurate time estimate, monthly payment difficulties, change orders, and inaccurate cost estimate. The effects of delays have been identified which time overrun and cost overrun were the most common effects of delays in construction projects. To minimize delays in construction project have been identified the top fifteen effective methods of minimizing construction delays from a total of thirty five methods.

V. Conclusions

This study successfully achieved its three objectives. The first objective was to identify the major causes of delays, their effects, and methods to minimize delays in construction projects. The analysis revealed a strong agreement between contractors and consultants regarding the ranking of delay factors, highlighting the significant impact of labor productivity on project delays. A total of fifty-seven delay-causing factors were identified, with the top ten including insufficient equipment, inaccurate time and cost estimates, monthly payment difficulties, change orders, poor site management and supervision, inadequate modern equipment, shortage of construction materials, incompetent project teams, and improper project planning and scheduling. These factors were grouped into eight categories, with contractor-related delays ranked as the most significant, followed by equipment-related, client-related, material-related, finance-related, consultant-related, external-related, and labor-related delays. The second objective, identifying the common effects of construction delays, was also accomplished. Six primary effects were found: time overruns, cost overruns, disputes, arbitration, total project abandonment, and litigation, with time and cost overruns being the most prevalent outcomes.

VI. Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Delays caused by contractors are often linked to low technical and managerial skills, particularly in developing countries. To address this, continuous training programs should be implemented to update personnel on modern project management techniques and enhance their managerial capabilities.

2. Reducing construction delays requires coordinated efforts among all stakeholders, including clients, consultants, contractors, suppliers, financiers, educational institutions, manufacturers, and government agencies. Establishing a participatory program through a dedicated national agency can strengthen the infrastructure and support needed for efficient industry management.
3. Most delays occur during the construction phase. To mitigate these issues, productivity should be increased through skill enhancement of human resources, more frequent site meetings, and a strategic approach that emphasizes effective management, knowledge and information flow across organizational levels, and active involvement of top management.
4. Utilizing modern construction equipment can reduce reliance on manual labor, increase task completion capacity, and minimize accidents and conflicts, thereby improving overall productivity.
5. A comprehensive project plan should be prepared before project execution. This plan serves as a blueprint or roadmap to measure progress at different construction phases and guide effective project implementation.
6. Project schedules should be realistic and accurate. Manipulated or unrealistic schedules may result in early or delayed completion, creating conflicts that contribute significantly to construction delays during implementation.

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